

EFFECTS OF CHEMICAL TREATMENT AND MIXING METHODS ON FRACTURE BEHAVIOUR OF HALLOYSITE-EPOXY NANOCOMPOSITES

S Deng, J Zhang, L Ye
School of Aerospace, Mechanical & Mechatronic Engineering
The University of Sydney, NSW 2006, Australia
Email: s.deng@usyd.edu.au

SUMMARY

Halloysite-epoxy nanocomposites were prepared *via* a chemical treatment processing and two mixing methods. Mechanical properties were characterized by compact tension (CT), tension and DMA tests. Noticeable improvements in mechanical performance of the nanocomposites were found and the possible strengthening and toughening mechanisms of halloysite particles in epoxies were identified.

Keywords: Halloysite, Nanotubes, Epoxies, Nanocomposites, Fracture toughness

INTRODUCTION

As a naturally existing clay mineral, consisting of unique tubular particles in submicron or nano-scales, halloysite has recently attracted some research attentions as a new type of additive for strengthening and toughening epoxies [1-3]. Tubular halloysite particles, mostly halloysite nanotubes (HNTs), are readily obtainable and are much cheaper than other nanoparticles such as carbon nanotubes (CNTs). More importantly, the unique crystal structure of HNTs resembles that of CNTs in terms of aspect ratio. There are obvious advantages in using halloysite as filler for polymer composites. First is the ease of processing, because halloysite particles are mainly discrete nanotubes with no or little surface charge. Such particles may eliminate the need for intercalation and exfoliation, as required by other two-dimensional nanoclay fillers such as montmorillonites (MMTs), to mix with polymers to produce homogeneous particle dispersion. On the other hand, halloysite belongs to the 1:1 type of the silicate clay family with a crystal lattice in each layer consisting of one aluminium octahedron sheet and one silicon tetrahedron sheet and with a monolayer of water in the interlayer positions. Certain surface modifications to halloysite may provide intercalations of halloysite layers with organic and inorganic compounds, which may provide the opportunity of exfoliation of individual layers, similar to those of organically modified MMTs. Preliminary results have demonstrated that blending epoxies with a certain amount of HNTs can noticeably increase their fracture toughness, strength and modulus, without sacrificing their thermal mechanical properties such as glass transition temperature (T_g) [2, 3]. However, achieving homogeneous dispersion of HNTs in epoxies remains a challenge due to agglomeration of large particle clusters [3].

It is believed that the agglomeration of HNTs is caused mainly by their relatively large surface energy because their tiny particle size results in a large surface area (specific

area = ~60 m²/g) [4]. As a result, HNTs tend to agglomerate under the influence of the van der Waals force. The moderate shear stresses provided by the conventional mechanical blending method are unlikely to fully eliminate particle agglomeration. However, the use of severe shear stresses may break up the agglomerates and achieve a homogeneous dispersion of HNTs in the polymer matrix. At the same time, as with organically modified MMTs, surface modifications to HNTs may produce the opportunity to expand the basal spacing of HNTs by the intercalation of inorganic and organic compounds in their interlayers, which may make it easy to obtain a homogeneous mixture of HNTs with polymers during blending. Furthermore, surface modification may also provide good wetting and bonding of HNTs with polymers.

In this paper, a chemical treatment process and two mixing methods were used to improve the homogeneity of halloysite particle dispersion in epoxies and to synthesise halloysite-epoxy nanocomposites. Mechanical properties of the nanocomposites were characterized by means of tension, CT and dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) tests and the possible strengthening and toughening mechanisms were identified by various analysis techniques including TEM, SEM, XRD and DSC.

EXPERIMENTS

Chemical Treatment of HNTs

Potassium acetate (PA), CH₃COOK, was used to treat HNTs to improve particle dispersion in epoxy resin and their compatibility. 11 grams of PA (Sigma-Aldrich, Australia) with a purity of 99% was mixed with 10 ml of hydrochloric acid (12 mol/l) and 1000 ml of distilled water in a glass beaker sitting on a hotplate stirrer to form a PA solution, and then 100 grams of halloysite particles were gradually added into the solution, stirring using a magnetic ceramic bar for 5 hours at 60°C. The mixture was then left in still condition until two apparent layers (liquid and solid) were formed in the beaker. The liquid layer was carefully removed before more distilled water was added to the mixture, followed by stirring again. The above procedures were repeated three times before the treated HNTs were finally separated from the distilled water and relocated into several flat glass pans for drying in a fuming hood at room temperature for four days until moisture fully evaporated. The dried particles were ground using a porcelain mortar and a pestle to crush the bulk agglomerates and then the ground particles were screened with a fine metal sieve.

Ball Mill Homogenisation

Although the typical objectives of the ball milling method include particle size reduction, solid-state alloying, and particle shape changes, blending using a ball mill has also been shown to be an effective method to produce a homogeneous mixture of polymer with additives [5, 6].

A planetary ball mill, Pulverisette 5 (Fritsch, Germany), was used to mix treated and untreated HNTs with epoxies. Prior to ball milling, both the treated and untreated halloysite particles were mechanically mixed with a diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (DGEBA) epoxy resin, Araldite-F (Ciba-Geigy, Australia), at 60°C using a mechanical mixer on a hotplate stirrer (IKA C-Mag HS7) and then transferred into grinding bowls

for further mixing using the ball mill. The ball mill consisted of four grinding bowls vertically positioned on a rotating supporting disc. During ball milling, centrifugal forces act on the grinding balls and the material in the grinding bowl due to the rotation of the grinding bowl about its own axis and due to the rotating supporting disc, which are expected to produce high shear forces to break up the agglomerates of HNTs. A master batch of halloysite-epoxy mixture (20% halloysite) was prepared with the use of 15 WC-Co grinding balls in 20 mm in diameter. A mixture volume up to 250 ml in each bowl was blended. A rotation speed of 200 rpm was used and the homogenisation process was programmed to run for 25 hours, with a 10 minute break every 30 minutes to avoid overheating.

Preparation of Halloysite-Epoxy Nanocomposites

Different amounts of the treated and untreated halloysite particles were separately combined with epoxy resin to form epoxy-based nanocomposites by means of two mixing methods, mechanical mixing with a mixer and homogenisation with the ball mill. In the mixing method using the mechanical mixer alone, HNTs were first washed using acetone and then mixed with epoxy by means of a mechanical mixer, stirring for 5 hours at 80°C. In the ball mill homogenisation, the master batch halloysite-epoxy mixture blended by the ball mill was first degassed in a vacuum oven (about -100 kPa) at 100°C for about 30 minutes and then further mixed with different amounts of neat epoxy resin, based on the weight percentages of the halloyiste in each sample group, stirring for 3 hours at 60°C by means of the mechanical mixer.

Subsequently, Piperidine hardener (Sigma Aldrich Australia) was added to the mixtures in a ratio of 100:5 by weight between epoxy and hardener, while stirring slowly. The mixtures were then degassed for about 10 minutes to remove possible air bubbles trapped during the mixing processes. Upon completion of degassing, the liquid mixtures were cast into specimen cavities in preheated silicone rubber moulds and cured at 120°C for 16 hours. Once the cured specimens were cooled and removed from the moulds they were milled using a surface grinder on both upper and lower surfaces to ensure flatness of specimens and, most importantly, to remove possible oversized halloysite particle agglomerates, which may sink to the bottom during curing. As a baseline for comparison, specimens were also prepared for the cured neat epoxy.

Characterisation of HNTs and Halloysite-Epoxy Nanocomposites

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM, Philips CM120 Biofilter) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM, Philips XL30 and Zeiss ULTRA) were utilised to identify the morphology of HNTs, particle dispersion in epoxies, failure modes and toughening mechanisms. TEM specimens with a thickness of around 90 nm were prepared by thin-sectioning using an ultramicrotome (Leica ultracut-S) with a diamond cutter. SEM observations were carried out on the fracture surfaces of compact tension (CT) and tensile specimens after sputter-coating with a thin layer of gold to increase electric conductivity.

The as-received and the chemically treated HNTs were examined by X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis (Siemens D5000) to characterise their crystal structures, especially

changes in the basal spacing, and by thermogravimetric analysis (Hi-Res TGA 2950, TA Instruments) to check their thermal stability. A differential scanning calorimeter (DSC) (2920 Modulated DSC, TA Instruments) was used to measure the thermal properties of the particles.

T_g of the cured neat epoxy and the halloysite-epoxy nanocomposites was determined by a dynamic mechanical analyser (TA DMA 2980) with temperature scanning from ambient temperature to 150°C at a heating rate of 3°C/min. A three-point bending fixture was used for the DMA measurements using specimens measuring 50 × 10 × 4 mm. A displacement amplitude of 20 μm was alternately applied with a frequency of 1 Hz for all DMA measurements.

The fracture toughness of the cured neat epoxy and the halloysite-epoxy nanocomposites was measured using a CT method according to ASTM D5045. To minimise the effects of residual stress and residual plastic deformation around the crack tip, a sharp pre-crack was introduced to each CT specimen by inserting a fresh razor blade at the end of the machined crack and tapping gently with a light hammer. A loading rate of 10 mm/min was adopted for all the CT tests, as recommended by the ASTM standard. Detailed information in relation to the CT tests has been previously described [3].

Tension tests were conducted to measure the basic material properties of the cured neat epoxy and the halloysite-epoxy nanocomposites. The tensile specimen had a dog-bone shape as required by ASTM D 638-99, with a cross section of 13 × 5 mm at the gauge length region. An extensometer with a gauge length of 50 mm was attached on the surface of the tensile specimen to determine the axial strain. A loading rate of 1 mm/min was selected for all tensile tests. At least five specimens were successfully tested for each sample group. The tensile modulus was derived from the slope of the stress versus strain curves of the tensile specimens in the initial linear elastic region. A similar range of the tensile stress, up to 20 MPa, was selected for the derivation of the tensile modulus, to ensure consistency for comparisons.

A universal material testing machine (Instron 5567) was used for both the tension and fracture toughness tests. All mechanical tests were conducted at ambient temperature (approximately 23°C).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Characteristics of Untreated and Chemically-Treated HNTs

X-ray diffraction analysis (Cu-K α) of as-received and treated halloysite particles was conducted and X-ray intensity patterns as a function of diffraction angle (2θ) are shown in Figure 1. The basal spacing [001] of the as-received halloysite particles is approximately 7.4 Å, and there is also a tiny 10 Å peak, indicating that the halloysite particles used in this study are mostly dehydrated (7.4 Å), with only a small amount of hydrated particles (10 Å). The chemical treatment with PA solution conducted in this study did not result in shifting of the 7.4 Å peak to the left, indicating that PA was unable to intercalate the already dehydrated halloysite used in this study.

Figure 1. XRD patterns of as-received and treated HNTs

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was conducted with a heating rate of 5°C/min and the results are shown in Figure 2 (left). For the as-received and the PA-treated halloysite particles, a weight loss of around 16% occurred after the temperature exceeded 500°C, representing the removal of the interlayer water, and there was a weight loss of ~3% during the initial stage of heating prior to 50°C, which was probably caused by dehydration of the particles with 10 Å basal spacing during the moderate heating [7]. Thermal analysis for the as-received halloysite was conducted by means of DSC with a heating (cooling) rate of 10°C/min up to 600°C (due to the upper temperature limit of the instrument). The DSC results for the original heating and reheating of the same sample are also shown in Figure 2 (right). Two endothermic peaks were detected during the first heating of the as-received sample. The results indicate that the major dehydration (loss of the interlayer water) occurred at about 580°C, whereas the dehydration of the particles with the 10 Å basal spacing occurred early at about 110°C. Once the material was heated to about 600°C, nearly all interlayer water was released, which can be seen from the DSC results of the reheating of the same sample where no endothermic peak was detected, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. TGA and DSC analysis results of HNTs

Generally, although the PA chemical solution used in this study did not play the part of intercalation, it was found that the chemical treatment using the PA solution effectively

reduced the size of the halloysite particle agglomerates, as most HNTs were still in the form of agglomerates rather than individual particles due to the influence of the van der Waals force. As demonstrated by the particle size distributions measured by a particle size analyser (Mastersizer, Malvern Instruments Ltd.) and shown in Figure 3, the size of the particle agglomerates for the PA-treated halloysite is obviously less than that of the as-received halloysite.

Figure 3. Size distributions of as-received and PA-treated halloysite particles

Effect of Mixing Method and Chemical Treatment on Dispersion of HNTs in the Cured Epoxies

The halloysite particles used in this study were mainly of tubular shapes with diameters varying in the range 10-600 nm and lengths 0.01-5 µm, as shown in Figure 4 (a). In the epoxy matrix, HNTs are mostly in the form of particle clusters of different sizes, as shown in Figure 4 (b) and (c). The surfaces of halloysite are commonly curved or rolled due to the misfit of the octahedral gibbsite-like sheets and the siloxane sheets, resulting in its unique tubular shape. The central cylindrical pores of small halloysite tubes are between 5 and 15 nm in diameter, and the centres of large tubes (> 1 µm in width) are largely filled [7]. Figure 4 (d) shows the cross-section of a large halloysite tube with a diameter of around 300 nm.

Typical fracture surfaces of CT specimens for the 10% halloysite-epoxy composites prepared by mechanical mixing and ball mill homogenisation are shown in Figure 5. The dispersion of HNTs in the halloysite-epoxy composites by mechanical mixing was generally uniform, though most were in the form of particle clusters of different sizes, shown in Figure 5 (a). There were also some isolated particle clusters of relatively large size up to several microns, particularly for the nanocomposite containing high halloysite contents. As shown in Figure 5 (b), the use of ball mill homogenisation greatly reduced the size of the halloysite particle clusters and resulted in more uniform distribution of HNTs.

Figure 4. TEM images of HNTs

Figure 5. Distribution of HNTs in cured epoxies (SEM photographs)

Figure 6 shows typical fracture surfaces of CT specimens near the pre-crack tip for the 10% halloysite-epoxy composites with three different surface treatments. It can be seen that there was a substantial reduction in the size of particle clusters on the fracture surface of the composite with 10 wt% PA-treated halloysite prepared by the ball mill homogenisation method compared to that of the composite prepared by the conventional mechanical mixing method, as evident in Figure 6 (a) and (b).

Figure 6. Fracture surfaces of CT specimens with 10 wt% halloysite (SEM photographs)

Effect of Mixing Method and Chemical Treatment on Fracture Behaviour of Halloysite-Epoxy Nanocomposites

The mechanical properties and glass transition temperatures of halloysite-epoxy nanocomposites prepared by two different mixing methods are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Mechanical properties of halloysite-epoxy nanocomposites

Materials	Tensile strength (MPa)	Tensile modulus (GPa)	Fracture toughness K_{IC} (MPa.m ^{1/2})	T_g (via tan δ) (°C)
Neat epoxy	64.8±1.8	2.89±0.09	0.92±0.04	97.0±1.9
5% HNTs (mechanical mixing, untreated)	67.3±2.0	2.93±0.09	1.26±0.04	96.2±1.9
10% HNTs (mechanical mixing, untreated)	67.4±1.9	2.98±0.10	1.35±0.05	94.7±1.1
5% HNTs (mechanical mixing, PA-treated)	68.3±1.8	2.92±0.07	1.27±0.06	95.5±0.8
10% HNTs (mechanical mixing, PA-treated)	68.6±1.4	3.05±0.18	1.39±0.10	97.1±1.2
5% HNTs (ball milling, untreated)	67.9±0.3	2.91±0.08	1.27±0.04	100.0±1.3
10% HNTs (ball milling, untreated)	69.1±0.2	3.05±0.11	1.35±0.03	100.0±0.6
5% HNTs (ball milling, PA-treated)	68.1±0.3	3.03±0.13	1.29±0.08	99.1±0.2
10% HNTs (ball milling, PA-treated)	67.8±0.6	3.21±0.13	1.39±0.04	102.2±0.9

The magnitudes of the critical stress intensity factor (K_{IC}) of the modified epoxies were significantly improved after HNTs were incorporated (5 wt% and 10 wt%), particularly for those composites prepared by the ball mill homogenisation method. For the

modified epoxy with 5 wt% HNTs, K_{IC} was increased 38%, from $0.92 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$ (neat epoxy) to $1.27 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$, whereas for the modified epoxy with 10 wt% halloysite there was a more apparent increase in K_{IC} , up to $1.35 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$, approximately 47% higher than that of the cured neat epoxy. From Table 1, it is evident that the composites containing PA-treated HNTs had increased strength, modulus and K_{IC} , compared with those of the cured neat epoxy and their untreated counterparts. The use of ball mill homogenisation in combination with PA treatment produced further improvement in mechanical properties, especially fracture toughness and strength. For example, the improvement in K_{IC} was as high as 51% for the 10 wt% halloysite-epoxy nanocomposite prepared by PA treatment in conjunction with the use of ball mill homogenisation, accompanied by increases in tensile strength (5%) and modulus (11%), in comparison with the properties of the cured neat epoxy.

Strengthening and Toughening Mechanisms of HNTs in Cured Epoxies

For the halloysite-epoxy nanocomposites prepared in this study, the improvements in fracture toughness and tensile strength can be attributed to two main mechanisms. One of them is the crack front pinning or bridging, due to the large aspect ratios of HNTs. The other is resulted from the interactions between the advancing crack and halloysite particle clusters [3], due to crack deflection and twisting, as well as plastic deformation [8].

Like in short fibre reinforced composites, individual HNTs, though tiny, should have crack front pinning or bridging effects because of their large aspect ratios, and can play the roles of fibre breakage, fibre debonding and pull-out, as shown in Figure 6 where those mechanisms are evident. As HNTs are much stronger and stiffer than the epoxy matrix, it is understandable that both strength and modulus were enhanced if the particles were evenly distributed in the matrix without the presence of large aggregations to cause premature failure.

Figure 6. Strengthening and toughening mechanisms of HNTs in epoxies: (a) debonding and breakage of HNTs, and (b) pull-out of HNTs

Interactions between the advancing crack and halloysite particle clusters also contributed to the improvements in mechanical properties, particularly fracture toughness. HNTs in the epoxy matrix occurred mainly in the form of particle clusters of different sizes, except for the fully separated individual particles. In those particle clusters, the epoxy resin can fully infiltrate into the clusters and provide wetting to the surfaces of the individual HNTs. These particle clusters, if their sizes are smaller than the critical size to cause a premature failure, can interact with the advancing crack at the crack front and resist its propagation under load, resulting in an increase in fracture toughness [3].

CONCLUSIONS

On the basis of the experimental results obtained in this study, ball mill homogenisation was demonstrated to be an effective method to decrease the size of halloysite particle clusters and improved the particle dispersion of HNTs in epoxies. PA treatment also reduced the size of the halloysite particle clusters, though intercalation of halloysite with PA has not yet been achieved in this study. With the improvement in particle dispersion in the epoxy matrix through ball mill homogenisation and chemical treatments, an increase of fracture toughness in terms of critical stress intensity factor (K_{IC}) of up to 51% was achieved for the 10 wt% halloysite-epoxy nanocomposite, accompanied by enhancements of strength, modulus and glass transition temperature (T_g). The strengthening and toughening mechanisms, including interaction between halloysite particle clusters and the advancing crack, interfacial debonding, hallosyite tube breakage and pull-out, were attributed to the enhancements in the mechanical properties of the nanocomposites.

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